

EMERGING THERAPY FOR DENGUE**Sajan Kumari*¹, Mrs. Jyoti Kumari² and Rajaram R. and Rajbhar*³**

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ABSTRACT

Dengue fever (DF) is an acute febrile disease caused by one of the four closely related virus serotypes of the genus Flavivirus, family Flaviviridae. Each serotype (DEN-1, DEN-2, DEN-3, and DEN-4) is sufficiently distinct that there is no cross-protection among them, and epidemics involving multiple serotypes may occur simultaneously. The disease is transmitted to humans primarily by the *Aedes aegypti* mosquito. Anti-dengue therapeutic approaches, such as host modulators, antiviral agents, and RNA interference (RNAi) therapeutics, are being investigated for the treatment of dengue. It is therefore essential to enhance understanding of the disease's prevalence, changes in viral strains, variations in the severity pattern, and the importance of early virus detection and disease management, which contribute to improved recovery outcomes. Population growth, rapid urbanization, increased international travel from dengue-

endemic regions, and global warming play major roles in the transmission and spread of the disease. Furthermore, several new vaccine candidates are under evaluation for their safety and efficacy in preventing dengue infection. This review highlights the nuances in the current standard-of-care treatment for dengue and discusses emerging therapeutic

strategies, antiviral drugs, and vaccines currently in various stages of preclinical and clinical development.

KEYWORDS: The disease is transmitted to humans primarily by the *Aedes aegypti* mosquito.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Dengue fever is the fastest emerging arboviral infection spore. Dengue has the most important arboviral infection world with more than 30 million. Dengue fever estimated to occur each year. The dengue virus is the cause of dengue fever. Dengue viruses are arthropod its born viruses (arboviruses) in the genus *Flavivirus*.^[1]

(Family *flaviviridae*) with the positive polarity. Single-stranded RNA. Is utilized *Aedes* (*stegomyia*) spp primarily. *Albopictus* as vector for domestic and peridomasti transmission. And arboreal *Aedes* vector for enzootic transmission of the *flavivirus* genus including other important pathogens such as yellow fever. Dengue viruses are the causative agent of a dengue fever. Its genome is about 11000 bases that the codes for three structural proteins (Membrane protein M, capsid protein C, and envelop protein E) and seven nonstructural protein it is also including the short non-coding region on both the 5 and 3 ends.^[2] The dengue virus genome is 11644 nucleotides in length, and is composed of three structural protein genes encoding the core protein (C), envelope protein (E), a membrane associated protein (M), and seven nonstructural protein (NS) genes. Nonstructural proteins is enveloped by glycoprotein, NS1 is of diagnostic and pathological importance. It is a 45 kDa in size and associated with it is cost by when *Aedes* mosquito carrying the virus bites a healthy person. This disease is mainly found in the tropical and subtropical regions of the world. According to WHO, an estimated 5,00,000 people require hospitalization each year. Most cases occur in tropical areas of the world, America most susceptible to the disease as per data released by directorate of National vector Borne disease. Currently there are no antiviral developed to treat dengue infection, and treatment remains supportive. Although a DENV vaccine has recently been used in some countries, Its indications is limited due to risk of severe dengue in certain populations. This has led to calls for intensified research efforts for development of novel vaccine, therapeutics and vector control strategies against dengue virus se control programme (NUBDPC).^[3] Currently there are no antiviral developed to treat dengue infection, and treatment remains supportive. Although a DENV vaccine has recently been used in some countries, Its indications is limited due to risk of severe dengue in certain populations. This has led to

calls for intensified research efforts for development of novel vaccine, therapeutics and difficulties in controlling the vector population control strategies against dengue virus.^[4,5] Whilst most of them recover from a simple febrile illness, a small but significant proportion go on to develop the dengue shock state with associated fatalities. In many affected areas, this adds up to a significant case fatality rate predominantly among young children and individuals of working age. The difficulty in controlling dengue infection stems from three root causes, ie, the presence of four different serotypes of virus, each with the independent ability to cause fatal disease, a lack of understanding of pathophysiology, nonavailability of specific treatment, nonavailability of a vaccine for prevention, and difficulties in controlling the vector population. There is no specific treatment for dengue other than supportive measures and judicious fluid therapy. Clinical trials have assessed various therapeutic options with minimal success over the last 50 years.^[6,7] The case fatalities in severe dengue are attributable to several factors. During epidemics, hospitals are overburdened with large numbers of patients, and close monitoring and management is extremely difficult given the limited resources in developing countries. In addition, the lack of understanding of the exact pathophysiology of dengue has led to a paucity of sufficient evidence-based management protocols aimed at specific pathophysiological phenomena of the illness. Many patients, due to lack of awareness, present late to hospital, sometimes in shock; their management is difficult, with a poor outcome. Due to practical difficulties in managing an established dengue infection, much emphasis is now placed on the prevention of transmission, by controlling vector populations. Various methods of vector control, ie, physical (removal of breeding places), chemical (insecticides and larvicides), and biological (use of bacteria such as *Bacillus thuringiensis*) have been used to control the transmission of disease.^[8]

Fig. 1: Dengue virus

2.0 History

In the 18th century, dengue has caused repeated epidemics worldwide.^[9] H. Graham in 1903 implicated *Aedes aegypti* as the vector for the disease and the virus was isolated in 1944 by Albert Sabin et al. Dengue haemorrhagic fever gained nosologic status in 1954 and subsequently it became an endemic in many areas of tropical Asia. India belongs to category B, where dengue is an emerging disease with cyclical epidemics becoming more frequent.^[10,11] The first record of a case of probable dengue fever is in Chinese medical encyclopedia from Jin Dynasty which referred to flying insects. The primary vector *A. aegypti* spread out of America in 15 to 19th centuries due to in part of increased globalization secondary to slave trade.^[12] There has been a significant rise in the number of epidemics and reported cases of dengue fever over the last 50 years. This represents an increase in detection rates with improved reporting, plus a true increase in incidence due to changes in environmental, climatic factors, and man-vector interaction. From 1955–1959 the average annual number of dengue infections reported to the World Health Organization was just 908 from less than 10 countries. From 2000–2007, the reported number was as high as 925,896 from more than 60 countries.^[13]

The natural history of dengue infection is fairly straightforward. The incubation period following inoculation of the virus is around 4–7 days.^[14] The symptomatic phase of the illness is divided into three phases, i.e., a febrile phase, a critical phase, and a recovery phase.^[15] In 1951, an American physician, Benjamin Rush mentioned about the probable dengue fever which occurred in Philadelphia, United States in 1780.^[16]

He named this fever as “break bone fever”-term which is synonymous to the pain the patients described they endured back then.^[17] A case of vertical transmission dengue virus was reported in Guangzhou, China. A 25 years old woman, 39 weeks pregnant was admitted in a general hospital. She experienced fever for 5 days and then gradually developed skin rash. She went into labour and delivered a girl. Results from ELISA dengue virus NS1 antigen test (Wantai, Beijing, China) and dengue virus fluorogenic quantitative PCR test (Liferiver, Shanghai, China) confirmed that both the mother and the baby suffered from dengue.^[18] Another study with 54 pregnant women was carried out in French Guiana between 2012 and 2014. Peripheral blood samples from the mothers, blood specimens from the newborns as well as the placenta was tested. The samples collected at each stage of the study was then used to carry out serological examinations i.e., reverse transcription polymerase chain

reaction (RT-PCR), identification of nonstructural 1 antigen (NS1 Ag) using Platelia Dengue NS1 Ag capture enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) (Bio-Rad laboratories, MarnesLa-Coquette, France), tests for specific dengue immunoglobulin using in-house antibody capture MAC-ELISA and also tests for dengue specific IgM/IgG antibodies using Panbio /IELSA (Panbio, Brisbane, Australia). Analysis of the serological and the molecular results suggested that vertical transmission is much more persistent if the mothers are infected at a later stage of pregnancy. Valid and appropriate tests must be carried out in order to detect vertical transmission of dengue virus.^[19]

Fig. 2: Transmission.

3.0 CAUSE^[20]

Dengue is caused due to four viruses, namely - DENV-1, DENV-2, DENV-3, and DENV4. The virus enters a mosquito when it bites an already infected person. And the illness is spread when it bites a healthy person, and the virus spreads through the person's bloodstream.

Types of Dengue

There are 4 sorts,

- DENV -1
- DENV -2
- DENV -3
- DENV -4

It has a place with the class flavivirus, family flaviviridae. (of which yellow fever infection is the sort species.) which contains around 53 infections.

Fig No. 3: Classification of Dengue.

4.0 SYMPTOMS

- Sudden, high fever-
- Severe headaches and pain behind the eyes-
- Nausea and Vomiting-
- Skin rashes- □ Low platelet count- □ Swollen lymph nodes-
- Severe joint, muscle and abdominal pain[20]

5.0 Spread

The Dengue virus is present in the blood of the patient. Suffering from Dengue fever. Whenever an aedesmosquitoes bites a patient of dengue fever, it sucks blood and, the dengue virus enters into its body. The virus undergoes further development of in the body of the mosquito for a few days. When the virus containing mosquito bites a normal human being (Healthy person), the virus is injected into the Healthy person body and he/she becomes infected and can develop the symptoms of dengue fever.^[21]

6.0 Life cycle

Until a few hundred years ago dengue virus it was transmitted in sylvatic cycle's in the Asia and Africa between mosquitoes of the genus Aedes and non-human primates with rare

emergences into the human population.^[22] The global spread of dengue virus, has followed its emergence from sylvatic cycles and the primary life cycle now exclusively involves transmission between humans and *Aedes* mosquitoes.^[23] Vertical transmission from mosquito to mosquito has also been observed in some vector species.^[24]

6.1 Life Cycle of dengue mosquito

Aedes aegypti is a so-called holometabolous insect. This means that the insects goes through a complete metamorphosis with an egg, larvae, pupae, and adult stage. The adult life span can range from two weeks to a month depending on environmental conditions. The life cycle of *Aedes aegypti* can be completed within one-and-a-half to three weeks.^[25]

Fig No. 4: Life cycle of dengue.

Fig-5 Reproductive Cycle of DENV virus in mediating viral pathogenesis.

6.1.1 Life stages of *Aedes aegypti* mosquito

- EGG-
- LARVA-
- PUPA-
- ADULT-

7.0 Methods of bioanalysis for anti-dengue activity

1. Pre clinical- Dengue is a positive stranded RNA virus with an 11kb genome, encoding a polyprotein precursor cleaved to generate at least 10 proteins, including three structural proteins (core, membrane associated protein, and envelope protein), and seven nonstructural proteins (NS1, NS2a, NS2b, NS3, NS4b, NS5). DENV is transmitted by silent, urban mosquito vectors. Including *A. albopictus* and *Aedes aegypti*, *A. polynesiensis* and *A. scutellaris*, to man. Other modes of transmission include via blood products, vertical transmission and organ transplant. In man, the initial cellular target of dengue is thought to be dendritic cells, followed by lymphatic spread and then distribution to macrophages and monocytes. The full host of cells infected *in vivo* remain a subject of investigation, but may also include hepatocytes, myocytes, and other cell types.
2. Clinical- Clinical methods for evaluation of anti-dengue effects are development. A major hurdle facing DENV clinical trial is the need for establishment of accurate diagnostic testing for case identification. The current diagnostics for DENV available in the US and other high resource countries (IgM and IgG ELISA, PCR) are limited by a requirement for skilled workers, specialized and refrigeration, equipment.^[9] Current point-of-care (POC) diagnostic tests for DENV. Based on lateral flow detection of secreted IgM and DENV NS1 protein in plasma/serum/blood.
3. RT-PCR for detection of Dengue viruses in clinical samples.^[26,27,28]

Figure 6: The immune response of the human body against dengue virus.

The immune response of the human body against dengue virus. *Aedes Aegypti* injects viral particles along with its saliva which infect the keratinocytes and other dendritic cells present near the skin. The infected cells represent the antigens of the pathogens on their surfaces, facilitating the recruitment of leukocytes. The infected cells migrate towards the lymph node to trigger the immune response. Soon after, more and more cells get infected and lead to viremia. The infected cells release interferons which aid the recruitment of B cells that release the antibodies, IgG and IgM and the cytotoxic T cells which target the infected cells. The complement system and NK cells are also recruited to neutralize the virus. The B cells also produce memory B cells in case the patient is infected again however, these memory cells will only be able to help if the patient is infected with the same serotype again.^[29,30] The figure was created using BioRender and exported under the terms of premium subscription.

8.0 Dignostic test flow chart

Fig. No. 7: Dignostic test flow.

9.0 TREATMENT

Agents in development for anti-dengue activity:

Direct acting antivirals

Nucleoside analogues

□ Balapiravir

A prodrug of the nucleoside analogue 4'-azidocytidine is a potent inhibitor of the in vitro replication of the hepatitis C virus (HCV). Once the parent compound has been delivered in the host cell and has been phosphorylated to its 5'-triphosphate metabolite, it acts as an inhibitor of the viral RdRp. An oral form, R-1626 (balapiravir), is rapidly converted to the active compound R-1479 and was found to suppress HCV infection in vitro and in vivo.^[29]

❖ RNA dependent RNA polymerase (NS5) inhibitors

N-sulfonylanthranilic acid derivatives were identified as DENV RdRp inhibitors through screening of one million compound. A novel class of compounds containing Nsulfonylanthranilic acid was found to specifically inhibit dengue viral polymerase. The structural requirements for inhibition and a preliminary structure-activity relationship are described. A UV cross-linking experiment was used to map the allosteric binding site of the compound on the viral polymerase.^[30]

❖ **Protease (NS2b-NS3) Inhibitors**

The viral nonstructural 2B and 3 (NS2B-NS3) protease complex is crucial for virus replication and hence, it is considered to be a good anti-viral target. Leaf extracts from *Carica papaya* is generally prescribed for patients with dengue fever, but there are no scientific evidences for its anti-dengue activity; hence we intended to investigate the antiviral activity of compounds present in the leaves of *Carica papaya* against dengue 2 virus (DENV-2).^[31,32]

❖ **Quinoline containing compounds**

Using virtual screening for DENV protease inhibitors followed by scaffold hopping, to expand chemical diversity, then a DENV luciferase reporter replicon assay, Deng *et al.* have described 17 new compounds with NS2b-NS3 protease inhibitor activity, which can now serve as potential lead structures for further discovery efforts.

❖ **Methyl transferase (NS5) inhibitor**

With the aim to help drug discovery against dengue virus (DENV), a fragment-based drug design approach was applied to identify ligands targeting a main component of DENV replication complex: the NS5 Ado Met-dependent mRNA methyltransferase (MTase) domain, playing an essential role in the RNA capping process. Herein, we describe the identification of new inhibitors developed using fragment-based, structure-guided linking and optimization techniques.^[33]

❖ **Capsid inhibitor**

Capsid-targeted viral inactivation (CTVI) has emerged as a conceptually powerful antiviral strategy that exploits viral structural proteins to target a destructive enzyme specifically into progeny virions.

No clinically approved anti-DENV drug is currently available. Here we report the high-resolution co crystal structure (1.5 Å) of the DENV-2 capsid protein in complex with an inhibitor that potently suppresses DENV-2 but not other DENV serotypes.

❖ **Peptide inhibitors of various DENV protein**

Inhibition of DENV attachment and entry to host cells by blocking DENV envelope (E) protein is an attractive strategy for anti-DENV drug development. A hydrophobic pocket on the DENV E protein is essential for structural transition in the membrane fusion, and inhibition of this process is able to inhibit DENV infection.

❖ **Mycophenolic acid**

Cellular autophagy (Macrophagy) is a self-degradative process, executed through the network of autophagy associated genes (ATGs) encoded proteins. Both in vitro and in vivo studies suggest that dengue virus (DENV) induces autophagy and supports the viral genome replication and translation.

❖ **Agents that target host mediated post translational modifications:- □ A Glycosidase inhibitors**

Cellular α -glucosidases I and II are enzymes that sequentially trim the three terminal glucoses in the N-linked oligosaccharides of viral envelope glycoproteins. This process is essential for the proper folding of viral glycoproteins and subsequent assembly of many enveloped viruses, including dengue virus (DENV). Imino sugars are substrate mimics of α -glucosidases I and II.

A major challenge in the development of iminosugar drugs lies in making a compound that is selective for the glycosidase associated with a given disease.^[34]

❖ **Vitamin D**

Vitamin D has a well characterized role in calcium and phosphorus homeostasis, but additionally has a role in the immune response to bacterial and viral pathogens. In this study a number of fused bicyclic derivatives of 1H-pyrrolo[1,2]imidazol-1-one with vitamin D receptor (VDR) agonist activity were evaluated for possible anti-DENV activity. The results showed that five of the compounds were able to significantly inhibit DENV infection.

❖ **Heparin and Heparin Sulphate**

Suramin effectively prevented dengue virus infection of target cells, indicating that the envelope protein-target cell receptor interaction is a critical determinant of infectivity. The dengue envelope protein sequence includes two putative glycosaminoglycan-binding We found that the cellular receptor utilized by dengue envelope protein to bind to target cells is a highly sulfated type of heparan sulfate.

❖ **Viral sensor (RIG-I and TLR3) agonists**

A growing body of evidence has demonstrated the role of components of innate immunity, including Toll-like receptors (TLRs), the retinoic acid-inducible gene I/melanomadifferentiation factor 5 (RIG-I/MDA5) and microRNAs (miRNAs) in the

recognition of dengue virus (DENV) or its components by infected cells. TLR3, TLR7/8 and RIGI/MDA5 sense genomic RNA or dsRNA, the product of an intermediate step of DENV replication, activating intracellular pathways leading to the production of antiviral effectors, including interferon and pro-inflammatory cytokines.

❖ Ivermectine

Ivermectin is an FDA-approved broad spectrum anti-parasitic agent that in recent years we, along with other groups, have shown to have anti-viral activity against a broad range of viruses. The anti-helminthic drug ivermectin it has been identified as an inhibitor of the nuclear importer import in α/β . Because DENV NS5 polymerase activity requires import in α/β , anti-viral properties of ivermectin were explored, and it is revealed that pre-treatment with ivermectin inhibited DENV infection of vero cells.

❖ Chloroquine

Chloroquine is an inexpensive, well-tolerated lysosomotropic 4-amino-quinoline derivative, which is well known as an anti-malarial drug but also possesses in vitro antiviral activity, including anti-DENV activity, potentially related to its effect of increasing endosomal pH.

❖ RNAi

RNA interference (RNAi) is an important antiviral defense response in plants and invertebrates; however, evidences for its contribution to mammalian antiviral defense are few. In the present study, we demonstrate the anti-dengue virus role of RNAi in mammalian cells. We observed down regulation of many known human microRNAs (miRNAs) in response to viral infection.

❖ Medicinal Plant

medicinal plants are always important part of traditional remedy and treatment sources for various diseases in India as well as worldwide. The medicinal plants are famous to their bioactive compounds, which are the rich source of pharmaceuticals, some of which contains good antiviral activity. The WHO and Ayurveda suggested that the use of medicinal plant extracts and their derivatives is helpful to fight against dengue disease.

9.1 Treatment of Shock

A protocol for intravenous fluid therapy has been developed by the World Health Organization (WHO) based upon clinical experience mainly in children from Southeast Asia.

11 For patients with shock, an initial bolus of five percent dextrose in normal saline or Ringer's lactate (10 to 20 mL per kg of body weight) infused rapidly is recommended, followed by continuous infusion (10 to 20 mL/kg per hour) until vital signs and urine output normalize. The infusion rate can then be gradually reduced until it matches plasma fluid losses. The adequacy of fluid repletion should be assessed by serial determination of hematocrit, blood pressure, pulse, and urine output. Patients with shock on presentation should initially have vital signs measured at least every 30 minutes and hematocrit measured every two to four hours. Narrowing of the pulse pressure is an indication of hypovolemia in children even with a normal systolic blood pressure. Normalization of the hematocrit is an important goal of early fluid repletion; however, a normal or low hematocrit may be misleading in patients with overt bleeding and severe hypovolemia. Close clinical observation is essential, even after normal blood volume is restored, because patients can develop shock for one to two days after initial fluid resuscitation, which represents the period of increased vascular permeability in DHF. Most patients who present for medical attention before profound shock develops and who receive appropriate fluid therapy will recover quickly. The fluids that are lost into tissue spaces during the period of plasma leakage are rapidly reabsorbed. Thus, intravenous fluid supplementation should be discontinued once patients are taking oral fluids and have normal hematocrit, vital signs, and urine output. Usually no more than 48 hours of intravenous fluid therapy are required. Excessive fluid administration after this point can precipitate hypervolemia and pulmonary edema. In the absence of complications from prolonged hypotension or from medical interventions, most patients with DHF will have stabilized within a few days of admission.

Discharge from the hospital is appropriate when patients have been afebrile for at least 24 hours and have normal oral intake, urine output, and hematocrit. The basis of DHF pathogenesis is hypothesized to be immunologic, which has led to interest in immunomodulatory drugs for therapy. However, a meta-analysis of four trials involving 284 participants found that corticosteroids were no more effective than placebo in reducing the number of deaths, the need for blood transfusion, or the number of serious complications.

9.1.1 Vaccination against dengue

The first dengue vaccine, Dengvaxia (CYD-TDV) developed by Sanofi Pasteur was licensed in December 2015 and has now been approved by regulatory authorities in ~20 countries. In November 2017, the results of an additional analysis to retrospectively determine serostatus

at the time of vaccination were released. The analysis showed that the subset of trial participants who were inferred to be seronegative at time of first vaccination had a higher risk of more severe dengue and hospitalizations from dengue compared to unvaccinated participants. As such, use of the CYD-TDV vaccine is targeted for persons living in endemic areas, 9-45 years of age, who have had at least 1 episode of dengue virus infection in the past. Several additional dengue vaccine candidates are under evaluation. The leading dengue vaccine candidate, ChimeriVax (Sanofi Pasteur), is a tetravalent formulation of attenuated yellow fever 17D vaccine strains expressing the dengue virus prM and E proteins.^[35] It has been difficult to develop a vaccine for dengue that is safe and elicits balanced neutralizing antibody responses to all four serotypes. However, in the past 5 years, remarkable progress has been made, and multicentre phase 2–3 clinical trials that are designed to determine the efficacy of this three-dose vaccine are under way. Data on immunologic correlates of immunity are lacking. Long-term follow-up of vaccinees will be essential to understand whether waning vaccine-elicited immunity predisposes recipients to more severe outcomes on subsequent natural infection. Other candidates in early phases of clinical development include vaccines containing live attenuated dengue viruses and recombinant subunit vaccines.^[36]

10.0 Prevention and control

At present, the main method to control or prevent the transmission of dengue virus is to combat vector mosquitoes through:

- preventing mosquitoes from accessing egg-laying habitats by environmental management and modification;
- disposing of solid waste properly and removing artificial man-made habitats;
- covering, emptying and cleaning of domestic water storage containers on a weekly basis;
- applying appropriate insecticides to water storage outdoor containers;
- using of personal household protection such as window screens, long-sleeved clothes, insecticide treated materials, coils and vaporizers;
- improving community participation and mobilization for sustained vector control;
- applying insecticides as space spraying during outbreaks as one of the emergency vectorcontrol measures;
- active monitoring and surveillance of vectors should be carried out to determine effectiveness of control interventions.^[37]

In the past 20 years, the prevention and control of Dengue DHF has become urgent with increasing geographical spread and increasing incidence. In order to ensure efficient case management, community based integrated mosquito control and appropriate use of vaccine where available, an efficient disease prevention programme must have many integrated and medical community education.

- 1. Active surveillance:** It is an essential component of a plan to avoid dengue. The aim should include the justification that emergency mosquito control programme can be introduced with an early warning or predictive capacity for disease transmission. Hospitals used as sentinel sites should include all patient in community who have significant infectious disease.
- 2. Mosquito control:** It is an essential component of a plan to avoid dengue. The aim should include the justification that emergency mosquito control programme can be introduced with an early warning or predictive capacity for disease transmission. Hospitals used as sentinel sites should include all patient in community who have significant infectious diseases
- 3. Community participation:** The focus nowadays is on community-based approaches .in order to attain community engagement, preventive programme need comprehensive health education.
- 4. prevention of Dengue in travellers:** Effective prevention of dengue fever is difficult to achieve for travellers visiting tropical areas. but it may greatly reduce the risk of infection. precaution include as follows:
 - Staying in rooms with screening or air conditioning.
 - To kill adult mosquito indoors, rooms are sprayed with aerosol bound insecticides.
 - Application of a DEET repellent on bare skin.
 - Wearing protective cloths.

10.1 Essential laboratory tests in assessing a patient's condition, the following tests are recommended

1. Haematocrit.
2. Serum electrolytes and blood gas studies.
3. Platelet count, prothrombin time, partial thromboplastin time and thrombin time.
4. Liver function tests serum aspartate aminotransferase, serum alanine aminotransferase and serum proteins. pressures for five minutes. The skin below the cuff is examined for

petechiae, and a finding of greater than 20 petechiae in a one square inch area is considered positive. Clinicians need to be aware that haemorrhagic manifestations can also be seen with dengue fever. In one study, a positive tourniquet test was noted at presentation in 36 percent of 28 children with DF; spontaneous bleeding may occur as well.^[37]

Food to eat

Dengue fever is an infectious disease caused by the bite of *Aedes aegypti* mosquito. The symptoms are fever and heat that occur within more than 3 days, and patients usually experience pain in the bones. To fight the dengue virus that infects the body, the immune system must be improved. The trick is to eat certain foods that contain lots of vitamins and nutrients.

Orange

This is one of the best fruit for people with dengue fever. Sweet orange or lime, also lemon, very well processed into juice because it is rich in vitamin C which helps the recovery of antibodies.

Papaya leaves

Doctors in India often give 2 tablespoons of papaya leaf juice in the morning and evening for dengue patients. This is a good medicine for the treatment of the disease.

Ginger Water

Basically dengue patients need lots of fluids. Give warm ginger water as a reinforcement of the body and reduce the effects of nausea that often they experienced.

Food to Avoid

Stay Away Junk Foods

Stay away from all type of junk foods. These foods are unhealthy and they emphasize the symptoms of dengue and fail to offer the essential nutrition for improved health.

Avoid carbonated soft drinks

Beverages like soda, carbonated soft drinks and beverages such as coffee and tea should be avoided.

Avoid alcohol and tobacco

Having alcoholic, tobacco and smoking should be avoided when suffering from high temperature.

CONCLUSION

Dengue is emerging as a global treat and is pressing public health priority in many countries. The government and the pharmaceutical industries have been taking initiative to develop new strategies to improve the diagnosis and treatment of dengue. The challenge here lies in how effectively the strategies developed are put into use. There also an obligatory need to globalize awareness and precautionary measures among the masses in order to control the incidence. Combined efforts of the health care industries, governing bodies and efforts at individual level would help us to tackle the prevalence of dengue.

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